

Preparation of Precipitated Metal Silicophosphates. Part-I. Low Temperature Synthesis of Aluminium Silicophosphates

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Complexation reaction of sodium metasilicate with a mixture of aluminium chloride and orthophosphoric acid has been studied in aqueous medium at 25°. Soluble salts of sodium silicophosphates are formed at three different pH values corresponding to monosodium dihydrogen silicophosphate, disodium hydrogen silicophosphate and trisodium silicophosphate during neutralisation reaction between sodium metasilicate and orthophosphoric acid. The presence of Al^{III} ions in this reaction shows precipitated aluminium silicophosphates of the compositions of Al(SiO₂)₂PO₄ and Al(SiO₂)_{1.5}PO₄ as salts of di- and tri-sodium silicophosphates. Infrared spectra of these compounds suggest coordination of oxygen atoms to Al, Si and P. Based on these studies, procedures have been developed for the synthesis of aluminium silicophosphates and these were characterised by analytical, IR and TGA data.

THE low temperature synthesis of aluminium silicophosphate involves a reaction of sodium metasilicate with a mixture of aluminium chloride and orthophosphoric acid in presence of sodium hydroxide or sodium carbonate in aqueous medium. Such a reaction has been employed in a few patented processes¹⁻⁴. In these processes, the quantity of sodium metasilicate or sodium hydroxide used is in large excess than stoichiometric requirement due to which an equivalent quantity of orthophosphoric acid is lost as sodium phosphate. Secondly, the product is contaminated with free silica. Hence, a systematic study was conducted to find out the theoretical quantities of reactants and the compositions of coordinated aluminium silicophosphate that may form at any of the three dissociation constants⁵ of orthophosphoric acid. The study has shown that aluminium silicophosphate of the compositions Al(SiO₂)₂PO₄ and Al(SiO₂)_{1.5}PO₄ corresponding to the second and third dissociation of orthophosphoric acid can be obtained.

Aluminium silicate has desiccant action on stored product insects by the removal of their water and lipid contents⁶ whereas tricalcium phosphate has physiological action on these insects in their larval stages⁷. A combination of the components of these two compounds has shown a wide spectrum biological activity with increased efficacy⁸.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. A Elico pH meter with combined glass calomel electrode was employed for pH measurements. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. TGA was carried out in static air using

a Stanton Redcroft 750/770 thermobalance, the heating rate being 10° per min. A Electro Selenium Ltd. (EEL) Flamephotometer was used for the determinations of sodium.

pH-titrations: Aliquots (50 ml) of 0.5 M orthophosphoric acid were titrated separately in replicates with 0.5 M sodium metasilicate solution at 25°. The pH values recorded after keeping the mixtures for 1 h to attain the equilibrium, were plotted against moles of Na₂SiO₃ added per mole of H₃PO₄. The plot (Fig. 1A) showed a characteristic trifunctional behaviour of orthophosphoric acid.

Aqueous solutions (50 ml) containing 0.5 M aluminium chloride and 0.5 M orthophosphoric acid were titrated with 0.5 M sodium metasilicate solution at 25°. The variation in pH values were recorded for each addition. The pH values were plotted against moles of Na₂SiO₃ added per mole of AlCl₃ or H₃PO₄. This showed a bifunctional behaviour (Fig. 1B) corresponding to the latter two dissociation of orthophosphoric acid.

Synthesis of aluminium silicophosphate: Equimolar amounts of aluminium chloride and orthophosphoric acid in an aqueous solution were mixed with equimolar amounts of sodium metasilicate and sodium hydroxide. A white amorphous precipitate of coordination compound of 1:1:1 aluminium silicophosphate was obtained (Table 1). Similarly, when 1.5 moles of aqueous sodium metasilicate were added to an aqueous solution containing 1 mole each of aluminium chloride and orthophosphoric acid, a white precipitate of coordination compound of 1:1.5:1 aluminium silicophosphate was obtained (Table 1). The aqueous solutions used throughout were of 0.5 M strength. The precipitates formed

TABLE 1—COMPOSITION OF ALUMINIUM SILICOPHOSPHATES SYNTHESISED AT 25° FROM AQUEOUS SOLUTION

AlCl ₃ : H ₃ PO ₄ : Na ₂ SiO ₃ : NaOH	Component	Composition %	Mole ratio Al : SiO ₂ : PO ₄
1 : 1 : 1 : 1	Al	12.50	1 : 1.04 : 1.02
	SiO ₂	23.90	
	PO ₄	45.00	
	Na ₂ O	0.54	
	H ₂ O*	13.00	
	Al(SiO ₂)PO ₄ ·1.5H ₂ O		
1 : 1 : 1 : 0	Al	10.59	1 : 1.51 : 1.02
	SiO ₂	35.60	
	PO ₄	38.00	
	Na ₂ O	0.76	
	H ₂ O*	15.00	
	Al(SiO ₂) _{1.5} PO ₄ ·2H ₂ O		

* Loss at 150°.

were allowed to stand for 1 h to attain equilibrium and were filtered, washed with demineralised water until free from sodium chloride and dried at 70°.

Composition of the material : A known amount (~500 mg) of powdered material was decomposed with concentrated perchloric acid (10 ml) by heating. The precipitated silica was separated on a weighed Gooch crucible, washed free of chlorate ions, dried at 110° and weighed as SiO₂⁹. The filtrate was analysed for aluminium and phosphorus by the standard procedures¹⁰. Sodium was determined by flame photometric method¹¹. Sodium ions might have been trapped in the framework cavities of aluminium silicophosphates.

TGA study : The thermogravimetric analysis of 1 : 1 : 1 and 1 : 1.5 : 1 aluminium silicophosphates showed an initial inflection point at 150° with the respective weight losses of 13 and 15% due to the removal of adsorbed water from the cavities of their framework. Further heating between 150° and 400° showed a small weight loss due to the condensation process. The number of moles (*n*) of water per mole of the compound was obtained from Albertis' equation¹²,

$$18n = x(M + 18n) / 100$$

where, *x* is the percent water and (*M*+18*n*) being the molecular weight of the compounds. On substitution, it showed the values of *n* as 1.51 and 2.07, respectively, for 1 : 1 : 1 and 1 : 1.5 : 1 aluminium silicophosphates.

Results and Discussion

Formation of soluble sodium silicophosphates : Orthophosphoric acid dissociates in three steps in aqueous solutions and accordingly its neutralisation with sodium metasilicate showed trifunctional behaviour (Fig. 1A). The appearance of three inflections on additions of 1/2, 1 and 3/2 moles of sodium metasilicate per mole of orthophosphoric acid corresponds to the neutralisation of one, two

Fig. 1. pH-Titration curves for (1) sodium silicophosphates and (2) aluminium silicophosphates: (A) 0.5 M H₃PO₄, and (B) 0.5 M H₃PO₄, 0.5 M AlCl₃.

and three hydrogen atoms of orthophosphoric acid in sequence,

The formulation of sodium silicophosphates are in agreement with the one Na_{4-x}(Si_{1-x}P_x)O₄ reported by Reau *et al.*¹³ as phosphorus and silica polymerise by coordination¹⁴.

Formation of aluminium silicophosphates : Addition of an equimolecular amount of Al^{III} ions altered the shape of the pH titration curves due to the displacement of hydrogen and sodium ions by Al^{III} ions forming a more stable 1 : 1.5 : 1 aluminium silicophosphate and may be as expressed by the equation,

The three-step neutralisation reaction (Fig. 1A) reduced to two-step in presence of aluminium ions (Fig. 1B), showing inflections at pH 9.0 and 13.20. This bifunctional behaviour indicated a combination of the first two steps into a single one¹⁵ at pH 9.0 (Fig. 1B), corresponding to the neutralisation of 2 hydrogen atoms according to equation (2) forming 2 : 1 : 1 sodium silicophosphate, which in turn was neutralised by aluminium chloride to give 1 : 1 : 1 aluminium silicophosphate according to equation,

The precipitate of 1 : 1 : 1 aluminium silicophosphate was unstable in the presence of HCl formed in reaction (5). Thus 1 : 1 : 1 aluminium silicophosphate synthesised by neutralising this HCl by equivalent amount of NaOH.

Fig. 2. Ir spectra of aluminium silicophosphates.

The second inflection at 1.5 mole of Na_2SiO_3 at pH 13.20 corresponded to the formation of a more stable 1 : 1.5 : 1 aluminium silicophosphate according to equation,

This was further confirmed by occurrence of the third inflection in the absence of AlCl_3 and the second inflection in the presence of AlCl_3 at 1.5 mole of sodium metasilicate. The 3 : 1.5 : 1 sodium silicophosphate formed at the third inflection (equation 3) in the absence of AlCl_3 interacted with AlCl_3 to form 1 : 1.5 : 1 aluminium silicophosphate according to the reaction,

at the second inflection point (Fig. 1B).

Hence, the overall reaction is a result of simultaneous reactions (1) between orthophosphoric acid and sodium metasilicate to form soluble sodium silicophosphates and (ii) between sodium silicophosphates and aluminium chloride for the precipitation of aluminium silicophosphates. The yields and chemical compositions (Table 1) also confirm the pairs of reactions (2) and (5) for the precipitation of $\text{Al}(\text{SiO}_2)\text{PO}_4$ and reactions (3) and (7) for $\text{Al}(\text{SiO}_2)_{1.5}\text{PO}_4$. These compositions are stoichiometric based on two ionisation groups of orthophosphoric acid and are different from those obtained by fusion method^{7,8} at 1400°. The infrared spectrum (Fig. 2) of 1 : 1.5 : 1 aluminium silicophosphate consists of (i) internal vibrations of the framework MO_4 tetrahedron ($\mu = \text{Al, Si, P}$) which show asymmetric stretch near 1090–920 cm^{-1} and M—O bending mode at 460 cm^{-1} and (ii) external vibrations which indicate asymmetric stretch near 1180–1090 cm^{-1} , symmetric stretch at 800 cm^{-1} and double ring at 520 cm^{-1} related to the external linkage between tetrahedra sensitive to the framework structure and to the secondary building units of polyhedra. These stretching modes of M and O

atoms indicate the formation of

structures^{14,15}. Since these compounds contain Al, Si and P in their compositions as central M cation, any change in composition would affect both internal and external vibrations by way of changes in the absorption bands. This is due to the difference in the distances of Al—O, Si—O and P—O bonds which cause additional vibrational modes¹⁶. As a result, the bands in the main asymmetric stretch region of 1 : 1.5 : 1 aluminium silicophosphate at 1180–1090 cm^{-1} envelope into broad peak in the corresponding asymmetric stretch at 1230–1010 cm^{-1} in 1 : 1 : 1 aluminium silicophosphate. This is accompanied by the reduction in intensity with increasing phosphorus and lowering of silica contents (Fig. 2). The ir spectra of these compounds are analogous to those of aluminosilicates coordinated with varying amounts of phosphate^{17,18} and silicate¹⁹. The ir bands at 1630 and 3450 cm^{-1} show the presence of coordinated and absorbed water molecules, respectively (Fig. 2). The low intensity broad 3520–3120 cm^{-1} band of 1 : 1 : 1 aluminium silicophosphate changed to a sharp 3450 cm^{-1} band in 1 : 1.5 : 1 aluminium silicophosphate due to the increased proportion of absorbed water^{18,20}. This was confirmed by the results of the TGA studies and compositions of aluminium silicophosphates (Table 1). These water molecules are responsible for acidic and catalytic properties of the substances²¹. These acid centres impart electrostatic field to the compound due to the dissociation of water molecules by cations. The increase in electrostatic potential due to the rise in dissociated absorbed water molecules showed enhanced insecticidal activity⁹.

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